

A Feature Space Maturity Model for ABM Frameworks

Luis Carlos Lara-Lopez, José Helo-Guzmán
School of Computing
Costa Rica Institute of Technology
Escazú & Cartago, Costa Rica
l3clara@gmail.com, jhelo@tec.ac.cr

Ignacio Trejos-Zelaya
Costa Rica Institute of Technology
& *Universidad CENFOTEC*
Cartago & San José, Costa Rica
itrejos@{ucenfotec.ac.cr, tec.ac.cr}

Santiago Núñez-Corrales
NCSA/IQUIST
UIUC
Urbana IL, United States
nunezco2@illinois.edu

Abstract—Agent Based Modeling (ABM) practice is constrained by the lack of systematic methods to evaluate and select frameworks for a given problem, and by the absence of protocols to study differences across computational implementations. These gaps may reflect inadequate renderings of theories by humans or by the frameworks themselves. This article addresses both challenges to reduce model brittleness when using different software tools for ABM research. We propose a Feature Space Maturity Model (FSMM), a set of numerical indicators derived from key ABM features to evaluate how well a framework matches the requirements of a modeling task. Although relevant, some of these features remain overlooked; our work highlights them directly. We present results of four canonical ABM experiments to demonstrate the FSMM applied to five well-known frameworks. Our results suggest that combining the FSMM with the proposed protocol provides valuable information for both framework builders and modelers facing complex technical and research choices.

Index Terms—agent-based modeling, ABM framework, ABM simulation, feature space, maturity model

I. INTRODUCTION

The effectiveness of agent-based models (ABMs) in complexity science [1], particularly in generative social science [2], lies in their ability to simulate emergent behavior through *bottom-up* abstraction [3]. By contrast, top-down simulation methods (e.g., dynamical systems, discrete event) require extensive parametrization and obscure the link between micro- and macro-scale dynamics [4]. These models are often *agentized* to better capture emergent phenomena [5]–[7].

ABM work usually begins with the conceptualization of agents and their interactions, producing models whose fidelity to reality [8] depends on feature selection. While absolute accuracy is elusive, ABMs aim to reproduce real agent behaviors and event distributions. Ideally, simulation outcomes should be independent of implementation details [9]. To ensure reliability, ABMs must scale to real-world systems and be run multiple times to capture average behaviors [10]. Yet most frameworks offer limited simulation features and rely on standard programming languages like Java [11], which mix model development with program writing.

Modern computational advances encourage frameworks to support robust simulation, analysis, and counterfactual experimentation. Such tools can improve model development, reduce errors, and enhance ABM’s accessibility and scientific

value [12]. Therefore, this paper introduces the *Feature Space Maturity Model* (FSMM), a scoring model for ABM framework features, with five experiments centered on classic ABM models¹.

II. ABM BACKGROUND

The use of ABM is heterogeneous. In some cases, designing various types of agents aims to validate the future operation of physical or virtual agents [10]. In other cases, the goal is to develop simulations that improve understanding of global or emergent phenomena in complex adaptive systems [13]. This distinction shows the need to identify key ABM concepts to evaluate current frameworks and propose a new reference architecture as a baseline for future implementations.

A. The need for ABM frameworks

Well-established models such as the Game of Life (GOL) can be coded in almost any programming language [14], but most collective behavior models are too complex to implement from scratch. To address this, many ABMs have evolved to share a common feature space for general-purpose modeling. An early example is the Simula 67 programming language, developed in the mid-1960s and widely used for research by the 1970s. It was the first language to automate step-by-step agent simulations [15] and included features such as objects, classes, and inheritance. However, it was a *programming language*, not a framework, and had important limitations for non-trivial models.

ABM frameworks aim to reduce the mismatch between model specifications and programming language capabilities. Over the years, many have been developed, ranging from lightweight frameworks with limited simulation capabilities to sophisticated ones with custom languages for simulation. Despite the variety of ABM frameworks available today, there is no common formal specification of the ABM feature space. This lack of standardization makes evaluation difficult. Frameworks ranked higher on our FSMM are expected to support more robust ABM development and greater fidelity to reality. In addition, the FSMM could serve as a baseline for future framework specifications. The next section lists the most

¹Source code available at: gitlab.com/msc_tesis/

critical elements of the feature space for ABM frameworks identified in our preparatory work.

B. Counterfactuals

Counterfactuals provide baselines to evaluate the possibility and impact of alternative explanations, represented as collections –or *ensembles*– of event timelines [16]. Counterfactual support means an ABM framework can generate and compare event timelines under different input parameters (e.g., treatments vs. control) across hypothetical scenarios [17]. It also includes cases where a model branches into different timelines from an initial configuration.

C. Framework limitations

We hypothesize that the absence of a rigorous evaluation model for ABM frameworks leads to substantial deficiencies in their implementations. This likely stems from the lack of adequate evaluation parameters (and ideally a reference implementation) to capture fidelity, quality, and utility of the resulting software artifacts. As a result, a perceived lack of capabilities often reappears, driving the specification and implementation of new ABM frameworks from scratch.

Maturity models in computing usually define six maturity levels per focus area [18]. Some of these (e.g., *repeatable, managed*) apply to organizations rather than specific software systems. Our FSMM instead follows the facilitator-based strategy proposed by Núñez-Corrales and Gasser [19], which defines ABM framework maturity as a gradient of technical facilitation with four levels: (0) no facilitators, (1) specific facilitators with high technical involvement, (2) general facilitators with low technical involvement, and (3) facilitators with no technical involvement.

III. FEATURE SPACE MATURITY MODEL

Our FSMM focuses on *simulation features, interrogation capabilities, and research support*. Although these features sometimes overlap, we minimized redundancy.

A. Simulation Features

The main purpose of an ABM framework is to allow users to build simulations in a robust and efficient way. The features described below define capabilities that support clear model implementation and high fidelity to reality. For example, a high-level programming language like Java without third-party libraries corresponds to level 0 in this sense. We selected five features under simulation: *usability, basic framework functionality, locality, agent management, and force field expressiveness*.

1) *Usability*: Usability reflects how easily an average user can install and use the framework. Although it is not formally part of the simulation category, it was included because of its significant impact on overall use.

0) No way to install. User must compile from source code. Very limited or no documentation.

1) Difficult to install, major stability issues. Basic documentation.

2) Generally stable with some minor issues. Useful and well-written documentation.

3) Stable and easy to install. Documentation covers all features and includes several working examples.

2) *Basic framework functionality*: This dimension qualifies the completeness of the framework’s feature set relative to potential use cases. It includes data processing, communication with external tools, and model validation against a specific problem formulation [20]. It also covers debugging tools such as visualization of control flow across a simulation, breakpoints, and conditional code execution. All these features improve model accuracy [21].

0) No standard framework functionalities. No support for random distributions. No ability to save simulation status. No support to read or write structured data files (e.g., CSV, JSON, TOML). No ability to stop simulation.

1) Ability to read/write files and handle structured data.

2) Ability to communicate with other tools for sending and receiving data, e.g., http/https support.

3) Ability to run a simulation conditionally with a truth value or by stepping. Ability to pause simulation to interrogate agents or their environment.

3) *Locality*: Many models of interest (e.g., geospatial) involve agents that need awareness of location, direction, and perspective in their environment. Spaces may be continuous or discrete, and described by a geometry and topology (e.g., planar, cylindrical, toroidal). An agent can occupy only one point or cell at a time, usually its center. In most ABM models, agents can modify only their visible (or reachable) surroundings, but non-local effects may be needed to capture information-driven collective behavior. Agents may also face inaccessible regions, useful to model exclusion conditions that are predefined or emergent.

0) All locality features must be implemented from scratch. No directions, no definition of agent neighborhood, and no support for spaces of any kind.

1) Basic locality features (e.g., agent position, simple spaces, simple topologies).

2) Support for discrete (i.e., grid-based) and continuous simulation spaces.

3) Rich locality and spatial features. Discrete and continuous spaces of any geometry and topology. Moore and von Neumann neighborhoods, as well as their extended versions [22], [23].

4) *Agent Management*: ABM frameworks must let users manage agents programmatically, including their creation, evolution, destruction, and housekeeping.

0) No agent construct. Agents must be implemented from scratch.

1) Basic agents available, but extra structures or logic are needed to manage them. Agents must be added to the scheduler and detailed logic is required to move them.

2) Full agent lifecycle management. Selection and filtering by agent types and locality are possible. Move actions proceed without additional structures or information.

- 3) Agents have internal communication structures (e.g., a mail-box [24]) coordinated with their internal time representation and scheduling, with peer-to-peer and collective primitives.

5) *Force fields*: Although uncommon in most ABM frameworks due to their specific uses [25], force fields are a powerful tool to capture complex interactions. They may arise from dynamical properties of the space agents inhabit or from agent actions that propagate across space.

- 0) No force fields. Additional data structures and algorithms required.
- 1) Basic force field support. Ability to define a point of emission and calculate distance and angle to it from a location in the space.
- 2) Agents and spaces act upon force fields. Forces have type and intensity and decay with distance. Multiple force types and emission points are possible. Point values and statistical properties of one or more forces are measurable at a location. The force range follows the geometry and topology of the space.
- 3) Ability to visualize forces at different levels of detail. Ability to show or hide forces by type and layer.

B. Interrogation Capabilities

The purpose of building models is to gain scientific insight by examining the consequences of their computation. Interrogation capability is therefore the second most important criterion in our FSMM, with an emphasis on *emergent behavior* [26].

1) *Visualization*: Visualization makes ABM results easier to interpret, which is essential given the complexity of the phenomena and the large amounts of data produced. It is also a useful tool for debugging.

- 0) No visualization support. Tools must be built using third-party libraries.
- 1) Limited visualization tools. Usually slow, poorly designed, but functional.
- 2) Fast, well-documented visualization. Option to disable visualization in favor of batch execution.
- 3) Comprehensive and well-documented visualization. Ability to visualize both detailed and statistical data, and to define layers by agent type, items, and force field attributes.

2) *Model-level statistics*: In a single simulation scenario, domain knowledge questions are usually answered through observables produced after model execution. ABM frameworks support this by tracking, storing, and exposing data interfaces for individual agents, their attributes, and the entire space when needed.

- 0) No statistical tools. Implementation entirely bespoke using third-party tools.
- 1) Basic support for statistical analysis. Main expected metrics: average, moving average, standard deviation, maximum, minimum, 95 and 99 percentiles. Basic ability to produce charts.

- 2) Well-documented chart interface (e.g., ability to define title, axis data, and min/max for grid).
- 3) Support for data streams, online analysis, and advanced statistical functions.

3) *Macroscopic support*: A key application of ABM models is understanding emergent behavior. We define emergence as the rise of surprising behavior in systems that cannot be analytically deduced or predicted from the properties of their constituents [27]. In our case, *macroscopic support* is the ability to compute metrics for ensembles of agents using statistical methods for analysis and storage, and possibly for comparisons across ensembles. One application is identifying when model implementations deviate from specifications. Detecting and correcting these deviations should improve overall fidelity to reality. Macroscopic statistical analysis also includes standard tests between two or more simulations [28].

- 0) Single execution only. Statistics computed for a single simulation scenario.
- 1) Execution and comparison of two scenarios at a time across macroscopic observables in real time over resulting data.
- 2) Orchestration of multiple simulations on different runners. Comparison of statistical behavior of macroscopic observables using various statistics.
- 3) Tools to collect, reconcile, and statistically analyze macroscopic observables across different simulations. Results stored in files and created by implementations in possibly different frameworks.

4) *Nearly decomposable system analysis*: Partitioning an ABM simulation into dynamical regions based on interaction density is essential for analyzing complex collective behavior [29]. Tools for nearly decomposable system analysis support hypothesis testing at the system level.

- 0) No concept of nearly decomposable systems. Identification of high internal and low external interaction must be implemented manually.
- 1) Ability to identify regions with many physically close agents in any space type (torus, plane, tube).
- 2) Ability to identify highly interacting agents through messages or events in their containing space.
- 3) Ability to visualize decomposable partitions based on interaction density.

C. Research support

Research support refers to the ability of a platform to facilitate hypothesis testing. While many ABM studies are exploratory, hypothesis testing advances the field by enabling computational instantiation of the scientific method [30], [31]. We selected three representative features: *graph support*, *counterfactual support*, and *utility features*. To our knowledge, these remain lacking in ABM frameworks; improving them would benefit ABM research by reducing the semantic gap between model specifications, implementations, and the hypotheses they aim to test. Due to the novelty and complexity of experiments requiring these features, they were not used

as scoring topics but are briefly described here as a basis for further research.

1) *Graph (network) support*: ABM models include relations between agents through events localized in time and space. Graph theory therefore provides valuable tools to analyze simulations as dynamical networks [32]. Useful metrics include centrality, clustering, and path lengths, which give insights into the system’s dynamics [33].

- 0) No support for graphs, neither algorithmically nor in visualization.
- 1) Basic graph capabilities (e.g., weighted graphs, path finding); ability to visualize graphs and relations as arrows or lines.
- 2) Ability to assign agents to graph edges as well as to the grid. Ability to define graph edges as curves and set the percentage of the edge covered by an agent.
- 3) Environment with multi-grid/multi-graph support. Edges can move agents between grids that can be stacked to simulate building floors, sections of space stations, etc. Agents can belong to multiple graphs simultaneously.

2) *Utility features*: Translating concepts and measurements from the scientific problem into experimental data defines commensurability between models and phenomena [34]. In practice, this link requires extra work that creates friction during ABM implementation. Providing a way to implement experiments closer to the specification should improve fidelity to reality and research productivity.

- 0) No research support features. Translation from specification values to implementation outcomes is manual.
- 1) Basic support for units of measurement (e.g., time scales, distances, intensities). Basic unit conversion arithmetic.
- 2) Ability to define and query resources using set theory and first-order predicate logic. Ability to capture complex behavior compactly.
- 3) Ability to define environments with several grid layers. Ability to mark cells as inaccessible for movement or information access. Ability to specify arbitrary grid topologies (e.g., Voronoi sets [35]).

3) *Counterfactual support*: Establishing causality, a key goal in complex systems research, requires testing hypotheses across primary and alternative scenarios [36], [37]. Counterfactual analysis is relatively new to ABM outside policy research [38], and its support in frameworks is limited. In practice, it requires defining multiple scenarios with the same model or generating new simulations from one simulation by branching through new parameter sets. The risk of combinatorial explosion—when branching logic creates too many possible worlds—must be controlled by a framework setting, such as a hard limit on concurrent branches.

- 0) Single model run for the entire simulation. Model branching must be implemented from scratch or is infeasible.
- 1) Simulation checkpointing available (i.e., stop, reload, restart).

- 2) Ability to orchestrate concurrent model executions with their initial parameters across runners.
- 3) Rule-triggered model branching. Ability to manage and orchestrate executions in new runners. Ability to remove macroscopically similar executions.

IV. TARGET ABM SIMULATIONS

Our selection of ABMs is informed by well-established literature in the field, their demonstrated significance across multiple domains, and the ratio between informativeness and complexity these exhibit.

A. Sugarscape

Sugarscape [39] provides a simple model of the impact of a resource-constrained environment on the emergence of economic and social behavior. Agents have a rich set of alternatives tied to their ability to consume or transfer resources, which determine their life cycle (Figure 1). The implementation used in our work involves a 150x200 torus grid with 150 agents of two equally distributed sexes, randomly scattered in the grid. Pairs of agents in the same location may reproduce successfully and acquire half the values per property from each parent but the same energy as the mother. Agents can take several actions during each time step. They consume sugar deposited in one grid as dictated by their metabolism, move toward resources or mates in proportion to their line of sight, or die of natural causes.

Fig. 1. Sugarscape implemented using NetLogo.

B. Predator-Prey Dynamics

The Lotka–Volterra –or *predator-prey* model- abstracts population dynamics resulting from the coupling of two interacting species, a prey and a predator [40]. This model and its limitations when applied to real biological systems has been amply studied; we invite the reader to consult the extensive literature around it. In short, the corresponding equations – assuming r stands for rabbits and w for wolves- are

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dr}{dt} &= \alpha r - \beta r w \\ \frac{dw}{dt} &= -\gamma w + \delta r w\end{aligned}$$

in which α and γ control for intra-species growth in predators and prey, while β and δ account for the effect of their interactions on reproductive rates. When agentized, continuous behavior of the system no longer hold due to the introduction of randomness in the interactions. This case is best captured by the autonomous Ito stochastic differential equations

$$\begin{aligned}dr &= (\alpha r - \beta r w)dt + \sigma_r r dW_r \\ dw &= (-\gamma w + \delta r w)dt + \sigma_w w dW_w\end{aligned}$$

in which σ_r, σ_w are noise intensities and W_r, W_w correspond to independent Wiener processes. Simulating these is computationally expensive due to pseudo-random number generation and not necessarily informative about the microscopic behavior of the system or the specifics of its interactions. Hence, this motivates applying ABM simulation to gain a deeper understanding about both. Figure 2 shows an instance of the predator-prey model implemented in Mason.

Our version of the model involves a 500x500 torus grid with 25 wolves and 250 rabbits. Wolves and rabbits reproduce asexually, rabbits reproduce exactly after 15 rounds, and predators reproduce after a successful hunt. There is no overlapping restriction for the grid. Wolves and rabbits are guided by forces applied only in their visible radius.

Rabbits have four forces, some of which are proportional to the respective Euclidean distances. First, a random directional force with intensity varying from 0 to 1, and spatially ranging 40° from 22.5° left to 22.5° right. Second, a flock force that groups rabbits together which grows linearly with the distance to each rabbit with initial intensity of 1. Third, a personal space force that repels a rabbit from its peers, which falls with distance with initial intensity of 40. Finally, rabbits experience a fear force repelling them from predators with intensity is 200 and no decay; it becomes 0 with no wolf in sight.

Complementary, wolves exhibit three different behaviors. With no rabbit in sight, the wolf will walk their maximum distance in random direction in search for rabbits. When one or more rabbits are in sight but not within walking distance, the wolf will walk in direction to the closest rabbit. When there is a rabbit in walking distance, the wolf will go next to the rabbit and eat it. The rabbit dies and the time to live for the wolf goes back to the maximum of 10 turns.

Fig. 2. Predator-prey implemented using Mason.

C. Economic Wealth Inequality

Modeling the dynamics responsible for wealth distribution is a fundamental question in economics [41] with implications for policy development worldwide [42]. Observations by Pareto on land ownership in Italy led to the formulation of the 80/20 principle [43]. Succinctly, the Pareto principle describes situations in which a small share of the causes explains a dominant portion of the observations. Empirical investigation [44] has resulted in various models with equivalent explanatory power.

For the purposes of our work, we chose a variation of preferential attachment as the underlying generating process of the observed power law distribution. Shortly, for N agents with wealth K_i , we expect their wealth to grow as a function of a power law exponent α and an accumulation bias γ ,

$$\frac{dK_i}{dt} = \alpha K_i^\gamma.$$

Assuming a constant increase in wealth c during each interaction, we can discretize the model assuming preferential Barabási attachment [45] as

$$K_i(t+1) = K_i(t) + c \cdot \frac{K_i(t)}{\sum_j K_j(t)}.$$

In our model, $K_i(t)$ is equivalent to exclusive tile ownership mediated by rent paid received across a grid of 100x100 tiles and $N = 100$; the number of agents remains fixed. Tiles have different (random) value, and rent exchange occurs as a result of agents entering a tile these do not own. The simulation starts with $K_i(0) = 0$ with an additional collection $c' = 75$ per time step. Rent is a random value r between 1 and 50 with tile purchase cost of $10r$. If an agent can afford to buy a tile it enters, it will do so. Otherwise, the agent will pay rent if possible, or pay the owner with accumulated wealth and tiles before any debt is forgiven. Successful purchases result in the value of the properties and rent to increase, resulting in migration of wealthy agents to expensive properties while owning as many tiles as possible. The simulation ends when no tiles can be purchased, and results of an experiment correspond

to ensemble simulations –e.g., computing statistics for 1000 runs. Figure 3 shows an example of this using Mesa.

Fig. 3. Pareto principle model implemented using Mesa

D. Pandemic Disease Spread

Recent events around COVID-19 and associated non-pharmaceutical interventions showcased the power of ABM simulations to plan –and act– at global [46] and local [47] scales. In reality, misinformation and other social factors [48] played a substantial role, which can be captured in ABM simulations of contagion processes with coupled spatial and network components [49]. We invite readers to consult the mathematical formulation of the Susceptible-Infected-Recovered (SIR) compartment model and COVID-19 extensions across extensive literature on the subject.

For our purposes, we produced a simplified model of 100x100 tiles with one agent each. Agents do not move across the grid and only interact via messages as described below. During each time step t , agents may become infected with a probability of $p_t = 0.21$. Agents can reduce their vulnerability by wearing a mask ($p'_t = 0.9p_t$), increase it by assuming immunity to the disease thanks to wearing an amulet ($p'_t = 1.1p_t$), or remain the same by choosing the ineffectual drinking of a glass of orange juice. We ensure $0.01 \leq p_t \leq 0.21$. At the onset, agents lack direct knowledge of the effectiveness of each measure, yet start with an initial trust level corresponding to their state of belief. Choices of measures are made using a roulette wheel algorithm of over these.

Belief update occurs by means of messages sent and forwarded across agents. The network contains up to ten whom the agent forwards messages to, and zero or more from whom it receives messages from. The messages contain trust levels for each measure. A weighted average across all incoming messages comprises the update rule for the belief state of the agent [50]. The update occurs during two time steps: one in which trust in influencers contributes up to 0.02, and another raising it to 0.03 in relation to the weighted average. Agents perform a single Bernoulli trial with the final value p'_t to update their contagion state. If infected, the agent decreases its confidence $c(m^*)$ by $c'(m^*) = 0.8c(m^*)$ and increases confidence in others $c(m)$ by $c'(m) = 1.01c(m)$. Otherwise, $c'(m^*) = 1.1c(m^*)$ and $c(m)$ by $c'(m) = 0.99c(m)$. After

this computation, agents forward their belief state to their forwarding contacts. We run the simulation across 1200 time steps and visualized trust level per measure (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Pandemic disease spread implemented using Mesa.

E. ABM simulations vs FSMM

Finally, we performed a mapping between each ABM simulation and the simulation features described in Section III-A. To do so, we extracted individual features required by each ABM simulation and obtained a qualitative picture of common and unique ones. We performed a similar exercise for interrogation capabilities in Section III-B. Results are summarized in Figures 5-6, which were used to elicit common modeling needs that ABM frameworks should help satisfy. We note that our results are also constrained by the extent in which our choice of models, which in our case disallowed a fair comparison across research support features. Later works will report results using models put in the context of actual hypothesis testing and requiring these features.

Fig. 5. Simulation features exercised by all ABM simulations.

Fig. 6. Interrogation capabilities exercised by all ABM simulations.

V. TARGET FRAMEWORKS

Five ABM frameworks were chosen to be evaluated with our Feature Space Maturity Model. Our selection is informed by their prevalence across the ABM research community, quality of documentation, historical relevance, and accessibility. At the onset, we selected Swarm for evaluation [51], released on November 1997 and its last stable release (version 2.4.1) is of April 2009. However, multiple technical obstacles ranging from limiting execution environments to availability of libraries resulted in its elimination from this research process. The following ABM frameworks constitute the basis of our analysis.

NetLogo [52]. First released on 1999, most recent stable version: 6.3.0, December 2021. It provides a multi-agent programmable modeling environment, and targets domain experts with limited or no experience in computer programming. Widely popular in education and research.

Multi-Agent Simulator Of Neighborhoods (MASON) [11], [53]. First released in 2003, most recent stable version: 22, July 2024. MASON is structured as a Java-based discrete-event multi-agent simulation library core intended to be highly performant. Simulations need to extend from the class `sim.engine.SimState`, and provides a lightweight basis to which users must add functionality. It assumes computer programming proficiency.

REcursive Porous Agent Simulation Toolkit. (Repast) [54], [55]. First released in 2003 (1.4beta), most recent stable version: Repast Symphony 2.11.0, July 2024. Repast models social actors as porous entities whose definitions benefit from object-oriented features inherited from Java. It contains advanced features, favors interactivity, and can be executed in single systems or clusters (Repast HPC). Repast uses Groovy – a wrapper over the Java programming language [56] usually distributed as a Plug-In for the Eclipse IDE Open Source Platform [57]. While not explicitly mentioned in their documentation, it appears that Repast re-implements all calls present in NetLogo.

Mesa [58], [59]. First released in 2015, most recent stable version: 3.2.0, May 2025. Mesa separates modeling, analysis

and visualization through an ABM library intended to facilitate both interactive simulation and batch processing. Its most recent version includes geospatial modeling capabilities, advanced scheduling modes, meta-agents and extensions.

Agents.jl [60]. First released in April 2019, most recent stable version: 6.2.10, April 2025. Agent.jl is implemented in Julia [61], aiming at high performance ABM simulations at scale. It is an open source, high quality software package with extensive documentation. Internally, it is structured via modular design and benefits from Julia’s functional programming style. Agents.jl provides rich spatial representation features, including access to Open Street Map data.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To achieve a comprehensive scoring of each framework described above, we implemented all four models independently and recorded the degree of maturity per feature under evaluation. The scoring system uses the scale from 0 to 3 as described in [19]. Results for simulation features (Table I) and interrogation capabilities (Table II) were tabulated and contrasted (Figure 7).

Feature	NetLogo	MASON	Repast	Mesa	Agents.jl
Usability	3	3	1	2	1
B. fram. funct.	3	3	3	3	3
Locality	3	2	3	2	3
Agent manag.	2	2	2	2	1
Force fields	0	0	0	0	1
Summary	11	10	9	9	9

TABLE I
FSMM SCORE ACROSS SIMULATION FEATURES.

Feature	NetLogo	MASON	Repast	Mesa	Agents.jl
Visualization	3	3	2	2	1
Mod. lev. stats.	3	3	3	3	3
Macrosc. supp.	2	2	2	2	2
Near. dec. sys.	0	0	0	0	0
Summary	8	8	7	7	6

TABLE II
FSMM SCORE ACROSS INTERROGATION CAPABILITIES.

At the start of our investigation, we included several additional candidate features in the FSMM. We later simplified and streamlined them to avoid conceptual overlaps. The usefulness of a maturity model depends largely on the practicality of its application and its ability to reduce ambiguity when used as an evaluation tool. The features described here are the result of our efforts in this direction.

Overall, support for force fields and nearly decomposable systems is largely missing from frameworks. Other features also vary in maturity. This may result from negative selection bias linked to domain problems, modeling scale (e.g., number of agents), and community practices. A possible explanation

Fig. 7. Scatter plot contrasting simulation feature and interrogation capability scores across all ABM frameworks using our FSMM.

is that frameworks—like other software artifacts—face evolutionary pressures from the incremental identification of needs. Depending on the initial software architecture, some needs are easier to implement in certain frameworks and harder in others. In this sense, software evolution is self-constraining. This fact alone justifies the value of this project: ABM framework builders must evaluate the whole feature space, not just niches.

Our results revealed important observations about the frameworks beyond the features captured by the FSMM. The long use history of both NetLogo and MASON appears to support their overall maturity. Users have had more time to create models and request features, pointing to a software–research co-design cycle of nearly two decades. Surprisingly, despite their recency, Mesa and Agents.jl are close in simulation features and continue to grow. Repast, although mature, requires dealing with the complexity of the Eclipse IDE at a programmatic level and includes some non-intuitive features. For Mesa, the version we tested showed slow interactive simulations in visualization, but the latest release has addressed these performance issues and remains to be tested.

Despite NetLogo being the most capable framework in terms of simulation support, writing certain behaviors remains challenging from a programming perspective. Its LISP-like internal language can be daunting for users more familiar with modern programming paradigms. This suggests that part of its success may be explained by sunk cost and technical debt among its users. In addition, the framework was designed for simulations to be contained in a single file, which is difficult for larger and more complex projects.

Agents.jl was somewhat disappointing because it has some basic deficiencies in rendering. Also, the simulation uses GIMakie which masked some failures and made debugging harder. Another issue was that starting simulations required at least 3 minutes of preprocessing in a high-end laptop. Starting with a ‘precooked’ environment decreased this time but did not remove it. Other frameworks started almost immediately.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The quality of inferences from ABM simulations depends on the adequacy of the models and the effectiveness of the tools. As models become more sophisticated—with more features needed for fidelity to reality and commensurability

of results—they face tensions with the capabilities of ABM frameworks. Not all frameworks are equally expressive for all tasks, reflecting the broader tension between generality and specificity in computing. However, because scientific discovery and exploration share common requirements, finding ways to measure frameworks against these needs is both meaningful and productive.

ABM has evolved over the last few decades into a tool with dual use: an educational testing ground for ideas about complexity and a virtual laboratory for fundamental and applied research. Certain scientific problems and communities have adopted ABM more readily because of the relational nature of the underlying phenomena, which sometimes creates the impression of restricted use and applicability. The COVID-19 pandemic drastically changed this view, as ABM simulations involved real stakes and became publicly visible. As a result, the ability of current and future users to assess existing ABM frameworks has gained importance in recent literature, even for those running on high-performance computing platforms [62].

Scoring the maturity of complex software is not easy. It is even harder for scientific software, where performance and correctness mix with reproducibility, accuracy, and research sustainability. More comprehensive scoring methods are therefore needed to address the challenges posed by ABM frameworks and simulations. Yet, the more comprehensive the scoring, the greater the risk of categorical overlap, as we experienced. The most important lesson is that the practicality of a maturity model matters most.

All ABM frameworks evaluated in this study shared a common set of features. Historically, ABM framework development has followed a path of mimicking useful features while innovating against those seen as inadequate. As in our exercise, assessing the overall fitness of a framework also depends on its routine uses. Our effort to replicate classical ABM simulations highlights the need for model implementations as transparent research objects [63] that can be inspected, shared, and criticized. Although we identified clear strengths and weaknesses across frameworks, further work in this direction is needed.

Our work suggests that a new generation of ABM frameworks will require a community effort to consolidate the elements evaluated here along with others (e.g., the ODD protocol [64]) into a substantial synthesis. The authors are pursuing ongoing work to develop a reference architecture based on the FSMM to address this challenge. It is also clear that, despite the flexibility of highly programmable frameworks, their role is to act as systems of constraint and opportunity that support scientific modeling.

Future technical work from our results follows three main paths. First, expanding the set of models and developing example scientific analysis pipelines around a hypothesis is needed to evaluate research support features. Second, we plan to report a rigorous statistical analysis of macroscopic behavior across different implementations of the same models, with an emphasis on relevance to scientific inferences. Third, our

FSMM outlines a path to build a formal reference architecture and create a proof-of-concept implementation that includes all features.

Finally, and on a more theoretical note, our FSMM is a simple evaluation tool based on numerical facilitator levels. A more powerful alternative would be to redesign it around the concept of focus area maturity models [65]. This approach seems particularly appropriate for ABM frameworks, since they evolve through periods of conceptual and technical expansion across diverse domains. It may also involve creating a rubric that details a minimum set of expected features for automatic assessment and comparison of models and frameworks.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank the the Costa Rica Institute of Technology's School of Computing Engineering for its support during the development of this work. S. N.-C. wishes to acknowledge continued support in ABM research from the National Center of Supercomputing Applications, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign. ITZ thanks Universidad CENFOTEC for their sponsorship and interest in the research reported herein.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Li Vigni, "Regimes of evidence in complexity sciences," *Perspectives on Science*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 62–103, 2021.
- [2] J. M. Epstein, *Generative social science: Studies in agent-based computational modeling*. Princeton University Press, 2012.
- [3] C. M. Macal, "Everything you need to know about agent-based modelling and simulation," *Journal of Simulation*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 144–156, 2016.
- [4] H. Sabzian, M. A. Shafia, A. Bonyadi Naeni, G. Jandaghi, and M. J. Sheikh, "A review of agent-based modeling (abm) concepts and some of its main applications in management science," *Interdisciplinary Journal of Management Studies (Formerly known as Iranian Journal of Management Studies)*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 659–692, 2018.
- [5] C. W. Seagren, "Examining social processes with agent-based models," *The Review of Austrian Economics*, vol. 24, pp. 1–17, 2011.
- [6] D. A. Robertson, "Agent-based models and behavioral operational research," *Behavioral Operational Research: Theory, Methodology and Practice*, pp. 137–159, 2016.
- [7] J. C. Stevenson, "Agentization of two population-driven models of mathematical biology," in *Conference of the Computational Social Science Society of the Americas*. Springer, 2021, pp. 176–189.
- [8] S. Núñez-Corrales, M. Friesen, S. Mudigonda, R. Venkatachalapathy, and J. Graham, "In-silico models with greater fidelity to social processes: towards abm platforms with realistic concurrency," in *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference of The Computational Social Science Society of the Americas*. Springer, 2021, pp. 155–169.
- [9] A. Antelmi, G. Cordasco, G. D'Ambrosio, D. De Vinco, and C. Spagnuolo, "Experimenting with agent-based model simulation tools," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 13, 2022.
- [10] F. L. Bellifemine, G. Caire, and D. Greenwood, *Developing Multi-Agent Systems with JADE*. John Wiley, 2008.
- [11] S. Luke, *Multiagent simulation and the MASON library*. George Mason University (CC), August 2019.
- [12] A. Batool, M. Bashir, M. Babar, A. Sohail, and N. Ejaz, "Effect or program constructs on code readability and predicting code readability using statistical modeling," *Foundations of Computing and Decision Sciences*, vol. 46, pp. 127–145, 06 2021.
- [13] C. Macal and M. North, "Agent-based modeling and simulation: Desktop ABMS," *Proceedings - Winter Simulation Conference*, pp. 95–106, 12 2007.
- [14] M. Gardner, "Mathematical games: the fantastic combinations of john conway's new solitaire game "life"," *Scientific American*, vol. 223, no. October, pp. 120–123, 1970.
- [15] K. Nygaard and O.-J. Dahl, *The Development of the SIMULA Languages*. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 1978, p. 439–480. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/800025.1198392>
- [16] N. J. Roese, "Counterfactual thinking," *Psychological Bulletin*, vol. 121, pp. 133–148, 1997. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.121.1.133>
- [17] B. D. L. Marshall and S. Galea, "Formalizing the role of agent-based modeling in causal inference and epidemiology," *Am J Epidemiol*, vol. 181, no. 2, pp. 92–99, Dec. 2014.
- [18] J. Becker, R. Knackstedt, and J. Poeppelbuss, "Developing maturity models for it management," *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, vol. 1, pp. 213–222, 06 2009.
- [19] S. Núñez-Corrales and L. Gasser, "Scalable social simulation: Evaluation of current frameworks and a new approach," in *Proceedings of the 2018 International Conference on Social Computing, Behavioral-Cultural Modeling, & Prediction and Behavior Representation in Modeling and Simulation (SBP-BRiMS 2018)*, 2018.
- [20] R. Sargent, "Verification, validation and accreditation of simulation models," in *2000 Winter Simulation Conference Proceedings (Cat. No.00CH37165)*, vol. 1, 2000, pp. 50–59 vol.1.
- [21] O. Balci, "Verification validation and accreditation of simulation models," in *Proceedings of the 29th Conference on Winter Simulation*, ser. WSC '97. USA: IEEE Computer Society, 1997, p. 135–141. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/268437.268462>
- [22] E. W. Weisstein, "Moore neighborhood," n.d., from MathWorld—A Wolfram Web Resource. [Online]. Available: <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/MooreNeighborhood.html>
- [23] —, "von neumann neighborhood," n.d., from MathWorld—A Wolfram Web Resource. [Online]. Available: <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/vonNeumannNeighborhood.html>
- [24] J. Cao, X. Feng, J. Lu, and S. Das, "Mailbox-based scheme for mobile agent communications," *Computer*, vol. 35, no. 9, pp. 54–60, 2002.
- [25] G. J. Maclay and M. Ahmad, "An agent based force vector model of social influence that predicts strong polarization in a connected world," *PLoS One*, vol. 16, no. 11, p. e0259625, Nov. 2021.
- [26] Z. Li, C. H. Sim, and M. Y. H. Low, "A survey of emergent behavior and its impacts in agent-based systems," in *2006 4th IEEE international conference on industrial informatics*. IEEE, 2006, pp. 1295–1300.
- [27] T. Holland, "Foundations for the modeling and simulation of emergent behavior systems," in *Engineering Emergence*. CRC Press, 2018, pp. 217–258.
- [28] D. Montgomery, *Design and Analysis of Experiments*. John Wiley & Sons, 2008. [Online]. Available: <http://books.google.de/books?id=kMMJAm5bD34C>
- [29] H. A. Simon, "Near decomposability and complexity: How," *The Mind, The Brain And Complex Adaptive Systems*, p. 25, 2018.
- [30] M. A. Janssen and E. Ostrom, "Empirically based, agent-based models," *Ecology and society*, vol. 11, no. 2, 2006.
- [31] A. Wilhite and E. A. Fong, "Agent-based models and hypothesis testing: an example of innovation and organizational networks," *The Knowledge Engineering Review*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 221–238, 2012.
- [32] A. Namatame and S.-H. Chen, *Agent-based modeling and network dynamics*. Oxford University Press, 2016.
- [33] E. of Mathematics, "Graph theory," 01 2024. [Online]. Available: http://encyclopediaofmath.org/index.php?title=Graph_theory
- [34] U. Wilensky and W. Rand, *An introduction to agent-based modeling: modeling natural, social, and engineered complex systems with NetLogo*. MIT press, 2015.
- [35] P. A. Burrough, R. A. McDonnell, and C. D. Lloyd, *Principles of geographical information systems*, 3rd ed. London, England: Oxford University Press, Apr. 2015.
- [36] P. Antosz, T. Szczepanska, L. Bouman, J. G. Polhill, and W. Jager, "Sensemaking of causality in agent-based models," *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 557–567, 2022.
- [37] A. Chopra, S. Kumar, N. Giray-Kuru, R. Raskar, and A. Quera-Bofarull, "On the limits of agency in agent-based models," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.10568*, 2024.
- [38] L. Blume, "Agent-based models for policy analysis," in *Assessing the Use of Agent-Based Models for Tobacco Regulation*. National Academies Press (US), 2015.
- [39] J. M. Epstein and R. Axtell, *Growing Artificial Societies: Social Science from the Bottom Up*. Brookings Institution Press, 1996.

- [40] P. J. Wangersky, "Lotka-volterra population models," *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, vol. 9, pp. 189–218, 1978.
- [41] Y. Berman, E. Ben-Jacob, and Y. Shapira, "The dynamics of wealth inequality and the effect of income distribution," *PLoS one*, vol. 11, no. 4, p. e0154196, 2016.
- [42] M. P. Todaro, "Review of Human Development Report 1992 by United Nations Development Programme," *Population and Development Review*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 359–363, 1992. [Online]. Available: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1973685>
- [43] V. Pareto, *Cours D'économie Politique*. Librairie Droz, 1964.
- [44] H. M. Hochman and J. D. Rodgers, "Pareto optimal redistribution," *The American economic review*, vol. 59, no. 4, pp. 542–557, 1969.
- [45] G. G. Piva, F. L. Ribeiro, and A. S. Mata, "Networks with growth and preferential attachment: modelling and applications," *Journal of Complex Networks*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. cnab008, 2021.
- [46] N. Ferguson, "Report 9: Impact of non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) to reduce COVID19 mortality and healthcare demand," 2020. [Online]. Available: DOI:10.25561/77482
- [47] S. Núñez-Corrales and E. Jakobsson, "The epidemiology workbench: a tool for communities to strategize in response to covid-19 and other infectious diseases," *MedRxiv*, pp. 2020–07, 2020.
- [48] M. M. Ferreira Caceres, J. P. Sosa, J. A. Lawrence, C. Sestacovschi, A. Tidd-Johnson, M. H. U. Rasool, V. K. Gadamidi, S. Ozair, K. Pandav, C. Cuevas-Lou, M. Parrish, I. Rodriguez, and J. P. Fernandez, "The impact of misinformation on the COVID-19 pandemic," *AIMS Public Health*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 262–277, Jan. 2022.
- [49] S. P. Mudigonda, S. Núñez-Corrales, R. Venkatachalapathy, and J. Graham, "Scheduler dependencies in agent-based models: A case-study using a contagion model," in *Conference of the Computational Social Science Society of the Americas*. Springer, 2021, pp. 56–70.
- [50] P. Bevington and D. Robinson, *Data Reduction and Error Analysis for the Physical Sciences*. McGraw-Hill Education, 2003. [Online]. Available: <https://books.google.co.cr/books?id=0poQAQAIAAJ>
- [51] G. Catalin Balan, "MASON: A Java Multi-Agent Simulation Library," 2009.
- [52] U. Wilensky and W. Rand, *An Introduction to Agent-Based Modeling: Modeling Natural, Social, and Engineered Complex Systems with NetLogo*, ser. The MIT Press. Cambridge: The MIT Press, 2015.
- [53] J. Gosling, B. Joy, G. L. Steele, G. Bracha, and A. Buckley, *The Java Language Specification, Java SE 8 Edition*, 1st ed. Addison-Wesley Professional, 2014.
- [54] N. Collier, "Repast: An extensible framework for agent simulation," *The University of Chicago's social science research*, vol. 36, p. 2003, 2003.
- [55] M. J. North, N. T. Collier, J. Ozik, E. R. Tatara, C. M. Macal, M. Bragen, and P. Sydelko, "Complex adaptive systems modeling with Repast Symphony," *Complex Adaptive Systems Modeling*, vol. 1, no. 1, p. 3, Mar 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1186/2194-3206-1-3>
- [56] K. A. Barclay and W. J. Savage, "Groovy programming : an introduction for java developers," Amsterdam, 2007. [Online]. Available: <http://www.books24x7.com/marc.asp?bookid=47160>
- [57] E. Burnette, "Eclipse ide pocket guide," Sebastopol, CA, 2005.
- [58] G. Van Rossum and F. L. Drake, *Python 3 Reference Manual*. Scotts Valley, CA: CreateSpace, 2009.
- [59] J. Kazil, D. Masad, and A. Crooks, "Utilizing Python for agent-based modeling: The Mesa framework," in *Social, Cultural, and Behavioral Modeling*, R. Thomson, H. Bisgin, C. Dancy, A. Hyder, and M. Hussain, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020, pp. 308–317.
- [60] G. Datseris, A. R. Vahdati, and T. C. DuBois, "Agents.jl: a performant and feature-full agent-based modeling software of minimal code complexity," *SIMULATION*, vol. 0, no. 0, p. 003754972110688, Jan. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1177/00375497211068820>
- [61] J. Bezanson, S. Karpinski, V. B. Shah, and A. Edelman, "Julia: A fast dynamic language for technical computing," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1209.5145*, 2012.
- [62] M. Fukuda, K. Wang, S. Panther, N. Wong, I. Dudder, and Q. Shao, "An analysis of three c/c++ cluster-computing libraries for agent-based models," *ACM Transactions on Modeling and Computer Simulation*, 2025.
- [63] T. McPhillips, C. Willis, M. R. Gryk, S. Nunez-Corrales, and B. Ludäscher, "Reproducibility by other means: Transparent research objects," in *2019 15th International Conference on EScience (EScience)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 502–509.
- [64] V. Grimm, S. F. Railsback, C. E. Vincenot, U. Berger, C. Gallagher, D. L. DeAngelis, B. Edmonds, J. Ge, J. Giske, J. Groeneveld *et al.*, "The odd protocol for describing agent-based and other simulation models: A second update to improve clarity, replication, and structural realism," *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation*, vol. 23, no. 2, 2020.
- [65] M. van Steenberghe, R. Bos, S. Brinkkemper, I. van de Weerd, and W. Bekkers, "The design of focus area maturity models," in *Global Perspectives on Design Science Research*, R. Winter, J. L. Zhao, and S. Aier, Eds. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2010, pp. 317–332.